

1 **New Insights into the Genetic Diversity of the Bacterial Plant**
2 **Pathogen ‘*Candidatus Liberibacter solanacearum*’ as Revealed by**
3 **a New Multilocus Sequence Analysis Scheme**
4

5
6 Ahmed Hajri, Pascaline Cousseau-Suhard, Pascal Gentit and Marianne Loiseau*

7
8 Plant Health Laboratory, ANSES, Angers, France.

9
10 **Abstract**

11 ‘*Candidatus Liberibacter solanacearum*’ (Lso) has emerged as a serious threat on solanaceous
12 and apiaceous crops worldwide. Five Lso haplotypes (LsoA, LsoB, LsoC, LsoD and LsoE)
13 have been identified so far. To decipher genetic relationships between Lso strains, a MLSA
14 study of seven housekeeping genes (*acnA*, *atpD*, *ftsZ*, *glnA*, *glyA*, *gnd* and *groEL*) was
15 performed on a representative bacterial collection of 49 Lso strains. In all, 5415 bp spanning
16 the seven loci were obtained from each of the 49 strains of our bacterial collection. Analysis of
17 sequence data was consistent with a clonal population structure with no evidence of
18 recombination. Phylogenies reconstructed from individual genes, and with concatenated data,
19 were globally congruent with each other. In addition to the five highly supported and distinct
20 genetic clusters, which correspond to the five established haplotypes, our phylogenetic data
21 revealed the presence of a sixth haplotype, designated ‘LsoG’. This new haplotype is currently
22 represented by two strains from France which had distinct sequences in four out of the seven
23 tested housekeeping genes. Altogether, the data presented here provide new information
24 regarding the genetic structure of Lso and the evolutionary history of the haplotypes defined
25 within this bacterial species.
26

27 **Running title:** ‘*Candidatus Liberibacter solanacearum*’ genetic diversity

28
29 **Keywords:** ‘*Candidatus Liberibacter solanacearum*’, genetic diversity, haplotype, MLSA,
30 apiaceous and solanaceous crop

31
32 *Correspondence: Marianne Loiseau, marianne.loiseau@anses.fr

33
34 Citation: Hajri, Ahmed, Pascaline Cousseau-Suhard, Pascal Gentit, and Marianne Loiseau. 2019.
35 "New Insights into the Genetic Diversity of the Bacterial Plant Pathogen '*Candidatus Liberibacter*
36 *solanacearum*' as Revealed by a New Multilocus Sequence Analysis Scheme." *bioRxiv*:623405. doi:
37 10.1101/623405.